

**THE FIGHT AGAINST TERRORISM IS REQUIREMENT
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Abstract. The purpose of the article is to analyze the terrorist threat both in the Republic of Uzbekistan and throughout the world, to identify problems resulting from terrorist activities. The goal is to determine methods of combating terrorist activities, primarily in terms of investigating criminal cases for crimes related to terrorism. The article uses comparative, logical-structural analysis, a systematic and multi-stage approach to solving the problem of terrorist activity. At the same time, it is noted that improving legislation, as well as conducting scientific research, are important directions in the prevention of offenses in this area. The results of the research conducted in this work can be used to understand the reforms being carried out in the country and determine the system for their adoption.

Keywords: terrorism, terrorist threat, security threat, fight against terrorism, cross-border threat, preliminary investigation, security measures, scientific research.

Currently, terrorism as a dangerous form of organized crime has become one of the most pressing and global problems at the international level.

As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev states, “The threat of religious extremism, terrorism, drug addiction, human trafficking, illegal migration and “mass culture” is increasing, undermining the beliefs and family values that have been supported by humanity for centuries. It is a fact and no one can deny that these and many other threats create serious problems in people's lives”¹.

Indeed, terrorism is one of the most dangerous and complex phenomena of our time, and over time it becomes more and more dangerous. This threatens security and socio-political stability and destroys the peaceful way of life in the country, can cause untimely death or threat to the lives of many innocent people, incalculable damage to the property of the state and

¹ From the speech of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the IV kurultai of the youth public movement “Kamolot”, Tashkent, June 30, 2017.

citizens, irreparable loss of material and spiritual benefits in the country, violation of human rights and freedoms, general unrest in the country.

The essence of terrorist activities is to achieve their malicious goals through the use of violence, terror and physical force against the dominance of the existing political, ideological, socio-economic order.

That is why terrorism is condemned by the entire world community and progressive forces. Terrorism is literally ignorance. International terrorism, based on subversive ideas, and all its manifestations place a heavy burden on the heads of all peoples, both in the past and in the present.

Every year, as a result of its aggression, more than 100 thousand innocent people die, it seriously threatens the development of society, some countries, regions and the progress of human civilization and causes terrible consequences.

In recent years, the threat of terrorism to humanity in the world has been characterized by a sharp increase in the danger to humanity, public safety, and is also characterized by the acquisition of a transnational and cross-border nature. The growth and spread of the arms trade around the world is also causing a rise in terrorism on a global scale. As a result of 1,787 terrorist attacks committed in recent years, 13,759 people were killed and 16,683 people were injured².

Terrorism also affected the people of Uzbekistan. In particular, as a result of the terrorist attacks committed in the city of Tashkent on February 16, 1999, 16 innocent people were killed, 130 people were injured of varying degrees of severity, material damage was caused in the amount of more than 700 million soums³, and more than 50 administrative and residential buildings were damaged⁴. As a result of terrorist attacks committed on March 29, 2004 in the city of Tashkent and in the Romitan district of the Bukhara region, on March 30, 2004 in the Kibray district of the Tashkent region, on April 1, 2004 in the Romitan district of the Bukhara region, on July 30, 2004 in the city of Tashkent, 38 people were killed innocent people⁵. On May 13, 2005, as a result of the terrorist attack in Andijan, 169 people were killed; during the armed

² Activities of the United Nations system in the implementation of the UN Global Counter-Terrorism Strategy, [//http://www.un.org/documents-dds/UNDOC/GEN/N1610252.pdf](http://www.un.org/documents-dds/UNDOC/GEN/N1610252.pdf); vavilon.ru/statistika-terrorizma/#statistika-terrorizma-v-mire.

³ Kodirov R. "Diniy ekstremizm va terrorism bilan bog'liq jinoyatlarni tergov qilishning ayrim hususiyatlari (amaliy qo'llanma). – T. O'qituvchi, 2000. – p.9

⁴ Karimov I.A. We build our future with our own hands. T.7. – T.: Uzbekistan, 1999. – P. 335.

⁵ G'oyibnazarov Sh. "Xalqaro terrorism: ildizi, omillari va manbai: Monografiya" – T., 2009. – p.251-252

attack, the terrorists seized 305 weapons, including 205 machine guns and 100 pistols, 231 grenades and other weapons⁶; they also released about 600 prisoners⁷.

Despite the fact that countries around the world are taking comprehensive measures to combat terrorism, new forms such as cyber terrorism, chemical poisoning, attacks using vehicles and sharp-edged weapons are becoming widespread, which pose a serious threat to the fate of humanity, its development and prospects, and has become a global international problem today.

“In the current situation, from the point of view of the interests of ensuring common security and achieving balance, the problems of security and sustainable development of the new independent states are of great importance. The situation and balance of power on earth are rapidly changing. New independent countries are emerging. And this today increasingly requires the search for new approaches to ensuring the stability of states and peoples, the development of new security models...”⁸.

Therefore, the need to use counter-terrorism capabilities, advanced methods and technologies is increasing, and the importance of improving the use of tactics and investigative methods in criminal cases related to terrorism is increasing.

Today it is necessary to pay special attention to scientific research to improve methods of combating terrorism, including the development of new tactical methods and opportunities for collecting evidence in criminal cases of this category.

In this regard, it becomes important to conduct pre-trial investigations of criminal cases related to terrorism, expand the possibilities of evidence during inquiry and preliminary investigation, develop means of ensuring the safety of employees at the scene of a terrorist attack, find scientific, theoretical and practical solutions to procedural and forensic problems encountered in national legislation and law enforcement practice related to ensuring human rights and freedoms during the investigation of acts of terrorism.

Our republic is implementing comprehensive reforms in order to reliably guarantee the rights and freedoms of individuals participating in criminal proceedings and to improve crime investigation procedures. The Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 clearly defined the task: “strengthening organizational

⁶ Narodnoye slovo. – 2005. – May 18

⁷ Narodnoye slovo. – 2005. – May 17

⁸ Karimov I. A. Uzbekistan on the threshold of the 21st century: security threats, conditions for stability and guarantees of development // Karimov I. A. On the way to security and sustainable development. T. 6. – T., 1998. – p.31.

and practical measures to combat religious extremism, terrorism and other forms of organized crime”⁹.

In the “Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026” many tasks are devoted to the fight against terrorism. In particular, Goal 70 states that it is necessary to protect young people from negative influences and trends, ideas of terrorism and religious extremism, as well as other trends that lead to the undermining of moral foundations. Goal 82 was named “Formation of effective mechanisms to counter extremism and terrorism,” which provides for the fight against terrorism not only at the national level, but also interaction with other states and international and regional organizations in terms of actions aimed at eradicating these threats¹⁰.

The “Uzbekistan-2030” strategy, in terms of reforms to strengthen the country’s defense security, indicates that it is important to protect the population from the influence of destructive ideas and prevent its radicalization¹¹.

This requires a comprehensive scientific study aimed at studying terrorism as a socially dangerous phenomenon with complex characteristics, improving methods and means of combating it, further developing a mechanism to ensure the inevitability of responsibility for a crime, further developing the fight against terrorism from the point of view of improving tactics and methods, these and other issues are among the pressing challenges of our time.

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⁹ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Uzbekistan UP-4947 “On the Action Strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan” dated February 7, 2017. Appendix 1, paragraph 2.4 // Collection of legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan. 2017. No. 6. Article - 70.

¹⁰ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-60 “Strategy for the development of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026” dated January 28, 2022, Appendix 1.

¹¹ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-158 “On the strategy “Uzbekistan-2030” dated September 11, 2023, Appendix paragraph 5.2 goal 96

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